

SUPPLIED TRANSFORMER TRANSDUCERS OF MECHANICAL VOLTAGE WITH DISCRETE OUTPUT

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Annotation: based on the analysis of patent and scientific and technical literature, the identified and classified generalized methods for improving the characteristics of mechanical stress converters are considered in the work, a method for converting mechanical stresses and a number of designs of transformer mechanical stress converters are proposed, which make it possible to increase the accuracy and speed of converting mechanical stresses into a code.

Keywords: transformer transducer of mechanical stresses (TMST); electromotive force (EMF); inductive transducer of mechanical stresses (IMN); automatic control system (ACS).

Overhead magnetoelastic transducers of mechanical stresses in automatic control systems.

Increasing requirements for automatic control systems for technological processes, as well as for devices and mechanisms, gave a strong impetus to the development of means of primary transformation and information processing.

Strain gauge and magnetoelastic methods are used to convert mechanical stresses into an electrical signal [1]. Since the tensometric method requires sticking strain gauges on the object under study, for ACS technological processes, the magnetoelastic method is mainly used, which makes it possible to convert both the magnitude and direction of mechanical stresses into an electrical signal [2].

The magnetoelastic method for converting mechanical stresses is based on the use of the connection between the magnetization of a ferromagnet and elastic deformations [3].

Fig.1. Classification of electromagnetic methods for converting mechanical stresses into an electrical signal

Figure 1 shows the classification of electromagnetic methods for converting mechanical stresses into an electrical signal. The study of the dependences of the magnetic characteristics of various materials on mechanical stresses showed that under the action of mechanical stresses, the shape of the hysteresis loop changes, namely, the loop is compressed or expanded with a simultaneous change in slope depending on the sign of the acting stresses [4]. Therefore, to convert mechanical stresses in structural steels with a relatively narrow hysteresis loop, the magnetic

permeability of the material is used as a measure of the change in magnetization due to mechanical stresses, and for alloyed steels with a wider hysteresis loop, the shape of the hysteresis loop, determined through the values of the amplitudes and phases of the higher harmonics contained in the electromotive force of the electromagnetic transducer [5], as well as the main characteristics of the hysteresis loop - the residual induction B_r and the coercive force H_c .

The dependence of magnetic permeability on mechanical stresses is expressed by the formula:

$$\mu = \mu_H \left[1 \pm \frac{3K_H}{K_1} \sigma_M (\lambda_{100} + \lambda_{111}) + \frac{2,25K_H^2}{K_1^2} \sigma_M^2 (\lambda_{100} + \lambda_{111}) \right]$$

However, experimental studies have shown that the dependence for structural steels with an error of no more than 0.5% can be represented as follows:

$$\mu = \mu_H (1 \pm K_\sigma \sigma_M)$$

Moreover, the value of the coefficient of magnetoelastic sensitivity K_σ is different for compressive and tensile mechanical stresses and can be determined experimentally or by calculation. For most structural steels, the K_σ value is in the range of 0.05....5 I/MPa [6].

Since only a few even or odd harmonics are used in the practice of converting mechanical stresses in ferromagnetic parts by the higher harmonic method, most of the information is not used. The paper proposes a conversion method based on measuring a large series (up to 100 points) of values of the hysteresis curve of a ferromagnetic material. In this case, the processing of information from the converter is carried out on a computer [7].

In a number of scientific papers, the results of using the Barkhausen effect for the transformation of mechanical stresses are presented, which consists in the influence of mechanical stresses on the spectrum of magnetic noise of a ferromagnet and the appearance of Barkhausen jumps due to the rotation of domain boundaries [8].

The methods listed above for converting mechanical stresses into an electrical signal are implemented using mechanical stress converters, which are a magnetic circuit or their system, covered by excitation and indication windings, with varying

magnetic conductivity. The active link of the transducers is the area of the surface of the object under study. The main characteristics of mechanical stress transducers are sensitivity to mechanical stress and conversion error [9].

Analysis of the research results of an inductive converter of mechanical stresses with a bridge circuit shows that the converter under consideration can be used to convert the components of a linear stress state, and high metrological characteristics (an error of no more than 4%) are provided when tuned to a narrow range of converted voltages [10].

From the analysis of works devoted to transformer converters of mechanical stresses used in the automatic control system, we can formulate the following requirements for converters:

- high sensitivity to mechanical stresses;
- small conversion error;
- high speed;
- the possibility of processing the signals of the converter with the help of a computer;
- the possibility of transforming the components of a complex stress state;
- manufacturability and ease of operation;
- low cost and high reliability [11].

Identification, analysis and classification of generalized methods for improving the characteristics of transformer mechanical stress converters.

The efficiency of the creative process of creating new designs of transformer converters of mechanical stresses with improved characteristics increases significantly if, when studying patent literature, i.e. at the stage of analysis of known technical solutions, generalized methods are used to improve the characteristics of transformer converters of mechanical stresses. As a result of the analysis of patent materials for the main classes of MKI G01B7 / 24, G01L / 12, as well as related - G01N27 / 86, G01R27 / 26, G01R33 / 12, according to the methodology, a number

of generalized methods for constructive improvement of transformer mechanical stress converters were obtained. The most important characteristics are: sensitivity, error of transformation of the direction of principal stresses. An analysis of the classification of generalized techniques shows that the largest number of generalized techniques for improving designs was developed in order to reduce the error due to the air gap, because this error is the largest in magnitude and essentially determines the value of the total error of transformer transducers of mechanical stresses [12]. The efforts of many researchers are aimed at developing effective methods for reducing the error of electromagnetic transducers from the instability of the air gap. Many of these methods were developed in connection with the development of electromagnetic methods for flaw detection, measuring the thickness of a product and other purposes, and in most cases for ferromagnetic controlled objects, these primarily include amplitude-phase, amplitude-frequency, phase, resonance methods, the method "equivalent" thicknesses [13]. One of the most common methods for reducing the influence of the air gap between the transducer and the ferromagnetic object under study is the two-frequency method, in which power is supplied by two voltages or currents of different frequencies, one of which (low) is used to transform the controlled physical and mechanical properties of the object, and the other (high) - to compensate for the effect of changing the air gap. The operating frequencies are chosen in such a way that the penetration depth of the high-frequency electromagnetic wave in the material of the object under study is significantly less than the penetration depth of the low-frequency one. The voltage at the output of the high-frequency channel serves as a control voltage for changing the gain in the low-frequency channel [14]. However, as studies have shown, the two-frequency method compensates for the multiplicative error, eliminating the loss of transducer sensitivity when the gap changes in the range of 0.1 ... 0.3 mm, but does not respond to the additive error, which leads to unacceptable errors in conditions of large gap changes. It is under conditions of a large change in the air gap that it is possible to eliminate its influence with the help of a special tracking system that maintains this

gap unchanged. The advantage of the method is a large detuning range, reaching up to 2...3 mm. However, such converters are very inertial, which hinders their implementation in ACS. The two-frequency method for improving the accuracy of electromagnetic transducers is a special case of a multi-parameter method in which the output value of the transducer depends on one informative and one non-informative parameter [15]. The essence of the multi-parameter method for improving accuracy is as follows. If the output value of the converter depends on two or more unknown parameters, then to eliminate the influence of non-informative parameters, it is necessary to solve a system of linearly independent equations, the number of which is equal to the number of unknown parameters. The considered essence of the method has found implementation in a number of designs of transformer converters of mechanical stresses of the compensation type. It should be noted that in linear transformer converters of mechanical stresses, in contrast to two-frequency electromagnetic converters, the geometrical dimensions of the magnetic circuit are the parameters that change [16]. The advantage of such transducers is the possibility of converting the components of a complex stress state. The disadvantage of the existing designs of transformer converters of mechanical stresses of the compensation type is low speed (10 ... 15 s) and a large error due to the influence of the air gap (8 ... 10%)

An analysis of the identified and classified methods for improving the design of transformer mechanical stress converters shows that the best characteristics are magnetoanisotropic mechanical stress converters, the output signal of which is proportional to the mechanical stress in two mutually perpendicular planes. The advantage of magnetoanisotropic transducers is their high sensitivity to mechanical stress and the absence of a systematic component of the additive error due to the influence of the air gap in the case of the location of the magnetic system of the transducer in a plane parallel to the surface of the object under study [17]. However, the fulfillment of the latter condition is a complex technical problem, which is currently being solved by complicating the designs of transformer mechanical stress

converters and increasing the conversion time [18]. A significant disadvantage of magnetoanisotropic transformer transducers of mechanical stresses is the transformation of mechanical stresses in parts with only a linear stress state [19]. Thus, the analysis of scientific and patent-technical literature has shown that for the transformation of mechanical stresses in objects with a complex stress state, for example, in main oil pipelines during their overhaul, the loading scheme of which can be simplistically classified as a bend with a shear force or in aircraft roller rings bearings when mounted on a shaft, the most promising are linear transformer converters of mechanical stresses [20]. In this regard, the urgent task of improving the design of transformer mechanical stress converters is to increase the speed and reduce the error due to the effect of changing the air gap between the converter and the object under study [21].

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